
ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF SMOKED FISH MARKETING IN OWO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, ONDO-STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Economic analysis of smoked fish marketing in Owo Local Government Area (LGA) was studied. The markets were selected randomly from towns in the LGA, smoked fish marketers were interviewed from each market with the aid of structured questionnaire and personal interviews. The data collected was analyzed using gross and marketing margin, regression analysis and descriptive statistics such as frequency, minimum and maximum values and percentages. Results showed that 71% of smoked fish marketers were young people between the ages of 18 and 39 years, 23% of them were of middle age, between 40 and 49 years. While the remaining 6% were old people above 50 years of age. Also, 94% of the respondents had formal education, while the remaining 6% were illiterates. The gender distribution had 98% women and 2% men. The gross margin analysis showed that smoked fish marketing was a profitable venture. In the study area, the high marketing margin of N189, 726.00 on the average suggested that the marketing of smoked fish was inefficient. The regression analysis showed that the coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) of 0.946 implied that about 94.6% of variation in the sales value of smoked fish in the study area was explained by the variables: age of respondents, level of education, experience of smoked fish sellers, operating cost and acquisition cost included in the model. The variables of age, experience, education and acquisition cost had positive sign and were each less than unity. This implied that each of the variables used was in Stage II of the marketing function and was efficiently allocated. The variables of operating cost was negative implying that it is in Stage III of the marketing function and was inefficiently allocated, the use of which should be reduced so that it can come back to Stage II. The identified constraints to effective and efficient marketing of smoked fish included inadequate and high cost of transportation and lack of good roads.

KEYWORDS: Economic analysis, *Clarias gariepinus*, smoked fish, marketing.

INTRODUCTION

Fish plays an important role because of its nutritional quality and its pharmaceutical uses. Fish is very good component to human beings as food, it is valued as a better source of protein than lean meat, it is easily digested and takes the place of meat as primary source of protein, FAO, (2001). It supplements the source of animal protein whose supplies have been declining due to scarcity of pasture as a result of desert encroachment meaning that only few animals can be kept for the supply of meat and other protein foods that would not meet the world's demand.

The agricultural sector would not have had difficulty in meeting most of the demand for goods, in terms of quality, quantity and variety but for the inefficient marketing systems, this is due to social and economic factors. The supply of domestic food such as fish, vegetable, fruits and other produce, vary as one would expect in a country with wide range of ecological conditions. Fish marketing in Owo LGA has generally been on a subsistence scale. The marketing of fish vary from one place to another, it also differs with the type of product whether fresh or smoked. In addition, the small scale fish farming seldom got beyond the village market and is generally sold to customers at the farm gate in the fresh state, but some people operating in medium or commercial scale have a direct point of delivery by the use of middle men, a common feature which cannot be eliminated in distribution and marketing network.

The idea behind marketing is simply to make the goods available to the final consumers, marketing is the performance of all business activities; it involves the flow of goods and services from the point of production until they are in the hand of the ultimate consumers, Berkeley and Darek, (1987). Marketing has authority in product planning, production scheduling and inventory control as well as in sales, distribution and servicing of produce. Marketing is often accused of creating high profit for the intermediaries between producers and consumers, as such; it is seen as being wasteful and inefficient, Dittoh (1985).

The nature of fish with respect to its perishability is of importance, the measures to put into consideration in preserving fish vary from individual to individual and these include freezing, smoking, salting, and sun-drying. Smoking involves the submission of fish to the action of wood smoke; the essence of smoking is to remove moisture content which is conducted in the traditional way with the use of kiln, oven, cement blocks, drums or iron sheet. After smoking, the fish gives characteristic flavor and appearance, the perishability nature of fish gives it the tendency to deteriorate quickly if not held in a special storage facility or processed, Bostock *et. al.*, (1987).

Smoked fish is marketed everywhere in the country and majority of the population demand for and make use of it. The demand is higher than the demand for red meat and other sources of protein, important consideration should be taken to develop the system of marketing smoked fish through research so that the consumers can be assured of continuous supply of smoked fish at good conditions at all times and at reasonable prices. The problems encountered in the marketing of smoked fish are: cost of transportation, lack of good storage facilities, poor electricity supplies, bad roads that are responsible for poor marketing efficiency. These problems constituted the focus of this study, with a view to improving the marketing of smoked fish in Owo Local Government Area of Ondo State.

METHODOLOGY

The Study Area

The field survey was carried out in Owo Local Government Area (LGA) of Ondo State, Nigeria, where economic analysis of smoked fish marketing was conducted. The major occupations of the people are farming and trading.

Sampling Procedure and Size

Data was collected from 100 smoked fish marketers that were randomly selected from 'Oja Oba' with the use of questionnaire which was administered on them.

Sampling Techniques

The study was based on primary data collected through the use of questionnaire administered using the interview schedule method. The personal visits to the selected fish marketers helped not only in getting the questionnaire filled, but also in obtaining other relevant information which could not be included in the questionnaire. Secondary data for the study were obtained from textbooks and journals.

Data Analysis

The data generated were analyzed using Gross Margin Analysis. The descriptive statistics used were frequency, percentages, minimum and maximum values of percentages. Also, inferential statistics such as regression model and test hypothesis assessing the significance of the explanatory variables on the revenue were used. Gross margin analysis was used to estimate the profitability of smoked fish marketing as represented below:

$$GM = GI - TVC$$

GM = Gross Margin

GI = Gross Income

TVC = Total Variable Cost

The Gross Margin is obtained by deducting Total Variable Cost from gross income obtained.

The Regression Analysis: the implicit function relating the income from smoked fish offered for sale to the factors affecting it, i.e. explanatory variables can be written as:

$$Y = (\text{LgAGE}, \text{LgEXP}, \text{LgEDU}, \text{LgA ACQCOS}, \text{LgSMO COS})$$

Where Y = Income from smoked fish offered for sale

LgAGE = Age of Respondent

LgEXP = Marketing Experience

LgEDU = Level of Education

LgA ACQCOS = Acquisition Cost

LgSMO COS = Smoked Fish Cost or Operating Cost

This function was fitted using regression double log. The estimated coefficients were subjected to further statistical tests for significance. The following tests of significance were carried out on the estimated coefficients, t-test, f-test, while R^2 and adjusted R^2 were computed to test for goodness of fit.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Age of Respondents

Age (Years)	Frequency	Valid %	Cumulative %
> 20	3	3.0	3.0
20 – 29	24	24.0	27.0
30 -39	44	44.0	71.0
40 -49	23	23.0	94.0
50 -59	6	6.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

Table 1 shows the age distribution of the respondents, 71% of the smoked fish marketers were young people between the age of 18 and 39 years, 23% of them were of middle age, between 40 and 49 years. The remaining 6% were older people above 50 years of age. It can be inferred from this table that smoked fish marketing in Owo LGA is dominated by young people. The rigorous activities involved in the struggle for smoked fish marketing might be the reason for this.

Table 2: Sex Distribution of Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Valid %	Cumulative %
Male	2	2.0	2.0
Female	98	98.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

Table 2 shows that 98% of the people involved in smoked fish marketing were females, while 2% were males. It is of note that the two males were single, i.e. not married. This implies that women were more involved in the processing, storing and marketing of smoked fish.

Table 3: Marital Status of Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Valid %	Cumulative %
Single	17	17.0	17.0
Married	78	78.0	95.0
Widow	3	3.0	98.0
Divorced	2	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

Data obtained from the respondents showed that 17% were single, 3% were widowers, 78% were married, while 2% were divorced. This shows that a high percentage of the smoked fish marketers were married.

Table 4: Level of Education of Respondents

Educational Level	Frequency	Valid %	Cumulative %
No Formal Education	6	6.0	6.0
Primary School	32	32.0	38.0
Secondary School	58	58.0	96.0
Others (B. Sc., NCE, HND)	4	4.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

From Table 4, 94% of the respondents had formal educational training which ranged from primary education to tertiary education. The remaining 6% had no form of formal education. The literacy level of the respondents made communication easy during the interview exercise as many of them were able to provide additional information to help the study as well as enabling them to trade in all parts of the country. The 6% that were illiterates mainly sell their goods in their own town alone.

Table 5: Experience of Respondents (Years)

Experience (years)	Frequency	Valid%	Cumulative%
Experience (years)	Frequency	Valid%	Cumulative%
1 – 5	50	50.0	50.0
6 – 10	42	42.0	92.0
11 – 15	6	6.0	98.0
16 – 20	2	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

Table 5 shows the number of years the respondents have put into the business of selling smoked fish. 92% had less than 11 years experience while 8% had between 11 and 20 years experience. From this, it can be deduced that most of the respondents had put few number of years into the smoked fish selling business, and this shows that they have little experience.

Table 6: Household Size of Respondents (Family Size)

Number of Children	Frequency	Valid%	Cumulative%
No Children	16	16.0	16.0
1 – 5	67	67.0	83.0
6 – 10	17	17.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

Results from Table 6 showed that 16% of the respondents had no children, while 67% of them had between 1 and 5 children. The remaining 17% had between 6 and 10 children. This implies that many of the respondents had small family size which may reduce pressure on their business capital.

Table 7: Problems Encountered in getting Smoked Fish to the Market

Problems Encountered	Frequency	Valid%	Cumulative%
Bad Roads	5	5.0	5.0
Cost of Transport – high	25	25.0	30.0
Lack of Vehicles	70	70.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

Table 7 shows that 70% of the respondents had problems with vehicles, 25% of them faced high cost of transportation while the remaining 5% were faced with the problem of bad roads. It implied that majority of the marketers were faced with lack of vehicles which hamper marketing of smoked fish.

Table 8: Nature of Market

Nature of Market	Frequency	Valid%	Cumulative%
Daily	78	78.0	78.0
Periodic	7	7.0	85.0
Weekly	15	15.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

From the Table 8, 78% of the smoked fish marketers sold fish on daily basis, 15% of the marketers sold on weekly basis while the remaining 7% sold on periodic basis. This implies that majority of fish marketers sold on daily basis due to regular demand of smoked fish. Only 7% of the marketers sold on periodic basis and it was observed that 15% of the marketers sold on weekly basis. This was observed to be higher than those that sold periodically.

Table 9: Categories of People Smoked Fish is Sold To

Categories of People	Frequency	Valid%	Cumulative%
Final Consumers	91	91.0	91.0
Retailers	5	5.0	96.0
Wholesalers	4	4.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

From Table 9, it is observed that 91% of the marketers sold fish to the final or end consumers, while 5% sold to retailers and the rest (4%), sold to wholesalers. It implies that sales are offered on a higher level to the end consumers, this boycotts both retailers and wholesalers, who as middlemen affect the prices of the product negatively on the part of the fish smokers.

Table 10: Pricing of Smoked Fish

Determination of	Frequency	Valid%	Cumulative%
Price			
Cost of Purchase plus margin	89	89.0	89.0
Previous sales	11	11.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

Table 10 revealed that 89% of the smoked fish sellers determined their selling price by cost of purchase plus profit margin, while the remaining 11% determined their prices from previous sales and demand status. Since majority of the respondents depended on the cost of purchase, the pricing of smoked fish in Owo LGA is largely dependent on the prevailing market situation in the LGA.

Table 11: Mode of Transporting Smoked Fish

Mode of Transport	Frequency	Valid%	Cumulative%
Motorcycle	96	96.0	96.0
Head load	4	4.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

From the Table 11, 96% of the respondents transported their smoked fish to the market mainly by motor cycle, while the remaining 4% transported their smoked fish by head load. This depicts that many smoked fish sellers depended on motor cycles for transportation in this area, this probably is due to bad roads and cheaper transport fares of motor cycles in comparison to taxi/ motor cars.

Table 12: Problems Encountered

Problems Encountered	Frequency	Valid%	Cumulative%
Poor demand	92	92.0	92.0
Loss due to spoilage	8	8.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

From Table 12, it was observed that 92% of the smoked fish sellers had problems of poor demand; this may be due to the fact that more people prefer fresh fish to processed fish. This could be adduced to the fact that the populace believes that only spoiled fish or left over fish are smoked for preservation against total loss. The remaining 8% of the respondents had problem of loss due to absolute spoilage. This is due to low patronage traceable to consumers' preference.

Table 13: Time of Highest Demand

Time of the Year	Frequency	Valid%	Cumulative%
November	1	1.0	1.0
December	99	99.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Market Survey, 2009

99% of the respondents had highest demand in the month of December while only 1% of the respondents had highest demand in November. This shows that consumption of smoked fish is very high in the month of December. It could be due to the fact that a lot of festivities go on during this period and this increases the demand for smoked fish which is eaten directly or used to garnish a variety of dishes.

GROSS AND MARKETING MARGIN ANALYSIS

Marketing margin is the difference in the prices paid for a commodity at different stages of the marketing system. Time, place, form and possession utilities are important factors that affect marketing margin. The overall marketing margin is the difference between the price paid by the consumer and that received by the producer. Marketing margin is usually expressed per unit of output, Johnson, (1985).

Gross margin on the other hand is the difference between the Gross income and Total Variable Cost, Acquisition Cost, Transportation Cost and Interest on Loan.

PROFITABILITY OF SMOKED FISH MARKETING

Gross marginal approach was applied by calculating the difference between total revenue and total variable cost.

$$GM = TR - TVC$$

where TR = Total Revenue

and TVC = Total Variable Cost

$$\text{Total Revenue} = P \times Q$$

where P = Price per carton of fish

and Q = Quantity of carton sold/month

thus TR per marketer = TR/N

GM per marketer = TR/N – TVC/N

where N is the total number of respondents.

The gross margin and marketing margin for the respondents is presented in the table below:

Table 14: Gross and Marketing Margin Analysis (Descriptive Statistics)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Cartons	100	120.00	288.00	211.32	61.1044
Transport Cost	100	12000.00	30000.00	18180.00	6176.4950
Acquisition Cost	100	432000.00	1036800.00	760776.00	218787.0018
Operating Expenses	100	19200.00	48000.00	29088.00	9882.3921
TVC	100	463200.00	114800.00	808044.00	219503.1517
Revenue	100	540000.00	1296000.00	950502.00	243394.7112
Gross Margin	100	30000.00	228000.00	142458.00	60365.4747
Market Margin	100	62000.00	259200.00	189726.00	57234.1119
GM per Carton	100	125.00	1770.00	711.57	339.7316
Market Margin Per carton	100	344.44	2160.00	956.73	365.9288

Source: Market Survey, 2009

Total Variable Cost = Acquisition Cost + Transportation Cost + Operating Expenses

Gross Margin (GM) = TR – TVC

Marketing Margin = TR – Acquisition Cost

From the table, the gross margin of smoked fish in the study area was N228, 000.00 and total variable cost was N1, 114,800.00. This shows that smoked fish marketing is a profitable venture in the area. The marketing margin is N259, 200.00 which is the price paid for marketing services. The size of the marketing margin reflects the structure and efficiency of the marketing system. A high marketing margin in the system is as a result of high cost incurred in the provision of marketing services.

ANALYSIS OF REGRESSION: Results and Estimates

The estimated function (Regression Double Log) chosen is summarized and presented in Table 15. This functional form fits the data because it has the following characteristics: the coefficient of multiple determination (R²) of 0.946 implies that about 94.6% of variation in the sales value of smoked fish in the study area was explained by the variables: age of respondents, level of education, experience of fish sellers, operating cost and acquisition cost, all of which are included in the model.

The variables of age, experience, education and acquisition cost had positive sign and were each less than unity. This implies that each of the variable use was in stage II of the marketing function and was efficiently allocated. The variable of operating cost was negative, implying that it is in stage III of the marketing function and was inefficiently allocated. Its use should be reduced so that it can come back to stage II.

Table 15 Estimates of Parameters of Marketing Function of Smoked Fish Marketing

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error
Constant	0.874	0.164
Age of Respondents	0.041	0.033
Marketing Experience	0.002	0.015
Level of Education	0.011	0.011
Acquisition Cost	0.856	0.021
Operating Cost	-0.001	0.020
R ²	0.946	
Adjusted R ²	0.943	
F - Value	327.306	
Standard Error	0.028	

CONCLUSION

Smoked fish marketing is a profitable venture in the study area. Smoked fish is nutritious and smoking makes the protein more available because of the removal of excess water from the fish. It is also a preservative measure against spoilage and deterioration. The socio-economic analysis showed that 71% of the respondents were young people between the age of 18 and 39 years, 23% of them were of middle age between 40 and 49 years, while the remaining 6% were old people above 50years of age. This implied that majority of the respondents were young people which means they are active in the marketing of smoked fish. The smoked fish market is mainly dominated by female with 98% and 2% were males. About 94% of the respondents had formal education, showing that many of them were literate. 92% of the smoked fish sellers had between 1 and 10 years experience, this confirmed that young and inexperienced people are in the business.

Smoked fish marketing in the study area was found to be inefficient due to numerous constraints facing it, these included lack of adequate transportation facilities and bad roads. The estimated Gross Margin was relatively high; Total Variable Cost was N111, 480.00 with N228, 000.00 of maximum value obtained. The estimated marketing margin was very high. Maximum value of N259, 200.00 was obtained as a further proof of inefficiency. The estimated regression coefficients carried positive signs except operating cost which implies that each of the variables used was in stage II of marketing function.

Five explanatory variables: age of respondents, marketing experience, level of education, acquisition cost and operating cost were used to estimate regression analysis. The variables of operating cost were negative, implying it is in stage III of the marketing function, hence its use should be reduced so it can come back to stage II.

The smoked fish market in the study area should undergo substantial modifications and improvements so that it would continue to render valuable services to the people.

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